

HISTORY OF ADDRESS IN THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10939740>

Annotation: This article studies the question of the origin and formation of addresses in the Russian language.

Key words: address, communicative, appellative, vocative, antiquity, case, syntax, person.

Address both as a unit of speech etiquette and as a syntactic figure constantly attracts the attention of researchers.

Address is one of the main means of a universal nature, developed by language to serve human communication, to establish a connection between the utterance and the subject of communication, to integrate different aspects and components of the communication situation into a single communicative act." Much attention has recently been paid to the communicative aspects of address, which is associated with the turn of linguistics towards pragmatics. Although sufficiently studied at the present stage of language development, circulation has practically not been studied in the diachronic aspect. Individual works on identifying the specifics of the use of addresses in works of one genre or one author do not give an idea of the development of the system of address throughout the history of the Russian language, while the address has gone through a complex path of development: the ways of expressing the address have changed over the centuries, the lexical composition has changed, the stylistic functions of the address varied depending on the era and genre of works.

One of the interesting and important problems associated with the history of conversion is the loss of a special vocative case in the Russian language. This question has been raised several times in Russian linguistics, but has not yet found an unambiguous interpretation. The vocative case has been preserved to one degree or another in almost all Slavic languages (the only exceptions are Slovenian and Russian), therefore, when deciding the reasons for the loss of the vocative case. It seems to us that it is necessary to take into account the data of related Slavic languages.

Initial concepts and terms. The term appeal in modern linguistics has several meanings. V. E. Goldin identifies 2 meanings: "Firstly, an address is a function of a service linguistic unit, which consists in emphasizing the direction of the text as a whole and its individual parts to the addressee, as well as in establishing correspondence between the addresser's and the addressee's ideas about the nature of socially typified relationships between them in the process of creating and perceiving the text. To say that a word (or expression) is "in the position of address" or "plays the role of address" means to indicate the specific function of the verbal unit in the text. Secondly, an address is a word (or expression) in the position of address, performing the functions of address, as outlined above." In addition, address can be understood in a broad sense as one of the ways of addressing speech.

The term appeal first appeared in "A Brief Guide to Eloquence" (1759) by M.V. Lomonosov: "Conversion is when we turn a word to another person, real or fictitious, from the one whom the real word itself requires." Lomonosov understood address in a broad sense as the address of speech in general and attributed it to the figures that decorate speech. Before this, the

direction of speech was discussed in relation to the vocative case.

In Russian linguistics of the 19th century, the address was considered together with the case forms of the noun and was not separated from the concept of the vocative case. For example, F.I. Buslaev pointed out that the address of the speaker's face to the listener is expressed by the name of the latter, placed in the vocative case. D.I. Ovsyaniko-Kulikovskiy spoke about the vocative case as a "word of address." From a syntactic position, he traditionally attributed the appeal to words and expressions that are not part of the sentence, but adjacent to it. In Soviet linguistics, the works of A.A. Shakhmatov deserve great attention. He, in particular, wrote: "An address is a word or phrase corresponding to the name of the 2nd person, the person to whom the speaker's speech is addressed. However, Shakhmatov did not go beyond the traditional opinion that the appeal "stands outside the sentence and is therefore not a member of the sentence." A.M. Peshkovskiy recognized that "material appeal can be closely connected with the rest of speech. However, formally, its main role of motivation does not give it the opportunity to enter into a connection of coordination, control or adjacency with any member of the sentence with which it stands, and it remains, no matter how widespread it reaches, a group extraneous to the given sentence." A.M. Peshkovskiy for the first time raises the question of distinguishing the address with the personal pronoun of the 2nd person and a similar separate application.

An interesting position is that of B.P. Ardentov, who singled out appeals as a special part of speech, pointing out that "a name, a title in the role of an address, is sharply different from a name, a title, which acts as a message about any facts. After all, if we consider the address of a noun as a noun, as is still done in grammar, then this creates extreme inconsistency in the syntactic functions of the noun: then the noun (as a subject, object, etc.) is a member of a sentence, serves as a means of expressing the objective material of thought and performs the function of presentation in language (i.e., it helps to describe some phenomenon or event); then it (as an address) is no longer a member of the sentence, serves as a means of expressing the subjective side of thought and is not able to perform the functions of presentation. The syntactic function of the so-called vocative case of a noun is also sharply different from other cases, which is reflected in the very morphological structure of its form, which also tends to exclude the vocative case form from the system of cases, i.e. to the exclusion of address (since its morphological form is the vocative case) from nouns." A similar point of view is expressed by N.I. Formanovskaya: "Addresses arise on the basis of words, but they themselves are not words. This is no longer a word-name (like naming a third person), but a communicative unit addressed to the addressee, i.e. a kind of speech action (speech act), consisting of calling and naming at the same time." In accordance with this, N.I. Formanovskaya does not consider the vocative to be a case, because the appeal is "not a word, not a lexical unit of language."

Studies of the syntactic nature of address prove that address is part of a sentence and is connected with its other members. A.G. Rudnev points out that "addresses, as a rule, are part of a sentence, therefore, they are grammatically and meaningfully connected with the rest of the sentence and, along with other members of the sentence, perform specific semantic functions in their inherent form - nominative case of a noun or substantivized parts of speech. The grammatical connection, which is characteristic of addresses, is <.> such a grammatical connection, which is expressed by the fact of the inclusion of defining words in the sentence and proximity to the defined member, but unlike agreement, control and adjacency, defining

words with a correlative connection receive their form on the basis of semantic connections with the entire sentence and its individual members and the syntactic functions they perform, regardless of the defined members of the sentence.”

This point of view is supported by A.T. Abramova. She, in particular, emphasizes that a sentence from the grammatical and semantic side represents an internal unity in which each component performs a certain semantic-syntactic function, being an organic part of this unity. “Understanding the sentence in this way,” the author writes, “we believe that the address, being in its composition (at the beginning, middle or end of the sentence), playing a certain role in it, determined by the meaning of the sentence as a whole, constitutes a structural part of the sentence and is its member. It is precisely the fact that the address, like other members, has a certain function in the sentence, naming the person of the interlocutor and often qualifying this interlocutor, the fact that the address is in a certain relationship with the sentence or with its individual members, gives us reason to see in it a special member sentences, correlative with other members. The address becomes aligned with other members of the sentence, while having its own specific features that do not allow it to be identified with either the main or secondary members.” O.A. Mizin offers a type of connection such as inclusion or contribution. “Introduction differs from both composition and subordination, although the internal structure of the introduced elements is built according to these types of connections. Thus, there is every reason, in our opinion, to consider an appeal a member of a proposal, which is characterized by introduction, the ability to “break” a proposal or to precede and conclude it.” M. Zatovkanyuk believes that an address is a member of a sentence, in particular it can act as a subject, but unlike the subject expressed by im.p., it denotes a subject taking part in a communicative act (good, friendly, pratsyuesh). The same point of view is shared by M.V. Fedorova and M.M. Naumova. In addition to studying the syntactic nature of address, the following directions can be distinguished:

- morphology of address: methods of expression (grammatical form) of address, “old” and “new” vocative forms;
- semantic changes in words in the function of address;
- communicative features of appeals: the functioning of appeals in real communicative acts;
- stylistic features of appeals;
- comparative study of the use of addresses as units of speech etiquette in different linguistic cultures.

Let us dwell in more detail on the morphological direction.

Traditionally, in academic grammar, the means of expressing address is considered to be im.p. a noun or a substantivized part of speech. In the Old Russian language, address was expressed by the star case (or vocative form), which was lost by the 15th-17th centuries. The vocative case, having lost its form, retained the function of designating the person or object to which the speaker is addressing, “and this function of the vocative case was not only preserved, but also received further development, expressed, however, by the nominative case.”

Vocative case in the noun declension system.

There are polar points of view on the question of whether a vocative is a case or a form of a noun: Traditional linguistics (starting with ancient linguists) classifies the vocative as a case category. Ancient grammarians identified 5 cases, including the vocative. “Due to the needs of those who speak, the cases are declined, so that the one who speaks about another can mark

when he calls, when he gives, when he accuses.” The Stoics identified the sound form “as a special type of utterance, the so-called “category of address”, which was not part of the system of cases. Alexandrian grammarians (Dionysius of Thracia), based on morphological features (special ending), introduced star. into the case system. The ancient teaching about language was adopted by Russian science. M.V. Lomonosov in “Russian Grammar” singles out the star. D.I. Ovsyaniko-Kulikovskiy considers the vocative case, noting the difference between the nominative and vocative cases from the rest: “Declination, taken as a syntactic process, must be, first of all, divided into two parts, sharply different from one another, belonging to completely different syntactic categories. One part consists of the nominative and vocative cases, the so-called direct ones, the first - as the case of the subject (subject), the second - as the “word of address”, and both do not relate to control (cannot be controlled); the second part is formed by the remaining cases, called indirect.” However, some linguists take the vocative outside the case system. For example, E.F. Karsky categorically states: “Pronouns that replace all forms of a name do not have a vocative case, which means it is not a case.” A.V. Isachenko believes that “the vocative form belongs to a different linguistic plane than the case forms. It is a form of “call” and is correlated with the imperative forms of the verb. In addition, the vocative form does not express any syntactic relations; it is, as it were, an inserted, interjectional member, not syntactically connected with the rest of the sentence. From the point of view of both syntax and morphology, the vocative form cannot be recognized as a case.”

The same opinion is shared by P.S. Kuznetsov, who writes that the vocative form “is more correct to be taken outside the case system, since it differs from the cases proper in that it does not express any relations in the phrase, but only represents an address.”

It is obvious that these points of view arose from different understandings of the category of case itself. “By a separate case of a noun,” wrote A.M. Peshkovskiy, “we understand a number of forms, united by a complex of heterogeneous, but equally repeated in each of these forms of meanings and having, at least in part of these forms, its own linguistic characteristics.”

According to V.V. Vinogradov’s definition, “case is a form of a name that expresses its relationship to other words in speech. <.> The case forms of a noun reflect an understanding of the connections between objects, phenomena, actions and qualities in the world of material reality” However, as V.P. Pronichev rightly points out, “the content of the category of case, a category that reflects the whole variety of connections between objects in reality , includes not only the designation of the idea of dependence, but also the idea of dominance of the name in the phrase. Recognizing this, the vocative should be considered a full participant in paradigmatic relations in the grammatical structure of the language.”

As E.V. Klobukov notes, “...the vocative in the modern Russian language does not have a single function that goes beyond the functional potential of the nominative: the vocative is just an optional means of expressing some meanings that the nominative case form has. But at the same time, “the nature of the semantics of the vocative does not contrast it with the rest of the case system. The specificity of the vocative lies rather in the limited scope of its use (colloquial speech), in its functional, formal and semantic secondaryity in relation to the nominative.” On the other hand, “if for at least part of the words of a given language or its functional variety the vocative is formally opposed to other cases (remember the general principles of establishing an independent case form established by A.M. Peshkovskiy), then there is no

reason to exclude it from the case system of this language."

However, apparently, in identifying the vocative as an independent case, its formal opposition to other cases is not the main criterion, because in languages where the vocative has a special grammatical design compared to other cases, it is also considered a case.

A.A.Potebnya differentiated them. and sound cases are not only based on endings: the vocative has syntagmatic characteristics of the 2nd person, while the nominative in a declarative sentence has the syntagmatic characteristics of the 3rd person. On this basis, in modern linguistics the idea of homonymy of the nominative and vocative cases is increasingly heard. O.A. Mizin believes that "we can only talk about a form perceived under the influence of written and printed fixation as the nominative case." L.I. Shapovalova identifies homonymous forms of the nominative narrative and nominative vocative, which have discrepancies in the meaning of the person.

It should be noted that the idea of homonymy to them. and sound cases was widespread. G.V. Ludolf, the author of one of the first Russian grammars, highlighted the star, noting that in colloquial speech it is similar to the nominative. N. Kurganov in the "Book of Letters," a practical guide to Russian grammar, also points out that "the vocative case of the singular is similar to the nominative case everywhere, except for God, God; Lord, Lord; Spirit, Soul; Jesus, Jesus." In addition, he notes star. and for adjectives (ibid., p. 19). Highlights star. and A. Barsov. This opinion also prevails in linguistics of the 19th - early 20th centuries. Only K. Aksakov argued that "the vocative case does not exist with us now."

In modern Russian linguistics, the work on the conversion of M.V. Fedorova and her student I.M. Naumova deserves great attention. In their joint work, they note "that in all cases of its use, the address is correlated, firstly, with the substantive nomination of the speech addressee and, secondly, with the pronoun you, as the bearer of the logical-conceptual nomination of the speech recipient. This pronoun is one of the members of that triad - speech inducer - recipient - object of speech/thought - which is precisely logical-conceptual, for it is represented in all languages of the world. <.> That is why in Russian texts of different periods both the appellative address or personal name and the pronoun you are used together, because significant words and personal names can be names of the object of speech, i.e. act in the third position of the logical-conceptual triad that we spoke about above." Further, the authors assert "that the solemn case has not been lost in the Russian language" and give it a new term - votive. Moreover, they also propose to consider the second person pronoun as an address: "In the construction You were already resting, Natasha, the words you and Natasha are equally necessary. In all such cases: you + Natasha have one morphological form, which is not nominative, but votive. In direct communication in Russian speech, only one of these words is usually used - either Natasha, or you, but each of them retains the form of a votive and can be called an address."

References:

1. Komarova Z.I., Khasanshina G.V. 2004. Latinized semantic metalanguage of agronomy as a way of scientific conceptualization and categorization of a fragment of the reality of the plant kingdom. In the book: Problems of linguistic conceptualization and categorization of reality. Materials of the All-Russian Scientific Conference "Language. System. Personality."

Ekaterinburg, UGPU Publishing House: pp. 27-43.

2. Aleshina E.K. 2009. Study of plant names and national linguistic picture of the world: towards the formulation of the problem. Bulletin of NSU. Series: History, philology. 8 (2): pp.34-37.
3. Isaev Yu.N. Phytonymic picture of the world in differently structured languages. dis. Dr. Phil. science Cheboksary, 2016. – 413 p.
4. Nevoit V.I. Phytonyms in the Russian linguistic picture of the world. In the book: Russian language: historical destinies and modernity. Materials of the International Congress. M., MSU: 2001. - P.154-144.
5. Fatkullina F.G., Kulsarina G.G. National features of the functioning of phytonyms in folklore texts. Scientific dialogue, 7 (55): 2016. - pp. 92-105.
6. Letova A.M. Semantic features of phytonyms in the Russian language. dis. Ph.D. philol. science M., 2012. - 198 p.
7. Klushin, N.A. Zoo- and phytomorphic characteristics of a person during conversations or speech: dis. ...cand. philol. sciences /N. Novgorod: Nizhny Novgorod State. ped. institute in. language them. N.A. Dobrolyubova, 1991. -161 p.
8. Giyosova, V. (2023). FEATURES OF THE COMPOSITION OF RUSSIAN AND UZBEK FAIRY TALES. Science and innovation in the education system, 2(5), 125-129
9. Avazovna, G. V. (2022). THE SOCIOLINGUISTIC NATURE OF THE ADDRESS. EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD), 7(7), 81-86.
10. Avazovna, G. V. (2021). Classification of fairy tales about animals according to their structural-semantic characteristics. Teaching Language and Literature, 1(8), 74-77.
11. Giyosova, V. (2023). FEATURES OF THE COMPOSITION OF RUSSIAN AND UZBEK FAIRY TALES. Science and innovation in the education system, 2(5), 125-129.
12. GIYOSOVA, V. (2019). Functioning of fairy-tale as one of the variety of folklore text in oral folk art. Scientific journal of the Fergana State University, 1(6), 124-126.
13. Akbarova, Z. A., & qizi Giyosova, V. A. (2023). Extralinguistic Means Of Expressing Appeal In The Uzbek Language. Texas Journal of Philology, Culture and History, 17, 9-13.
14. Giyosova, V. A. (2022). CONCEPT IN MODERN LINGUOCULTUROLOGY. ILM FAN TARAQQIYOTIDA ZAMONAVIY METODLARNING QO'LLANILISHI, 2(28), 161-166.
15. kizi Giyosova, V. A. (2022). TOTEMISTIC ORIGIN OF TALES ABOUT ANIMALS. THE ROLE OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE MODERN WORLD, 1(1), 133-139.
16. Giyosova, V. A. (2023, October). FORMATION OF THE DICTIONARY OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN. In International Conference on Multidisciplinary Research (Vol. 1, No. 6, pp. 103-105).
17. Giyosova V. SOCIOLINGUISTIC ANALYSIS OF REFERENCE UNITS. Farg 'ona davlat universiteti ilmiy jurnali. 2023 Feb 25(1):512-6.
18. Giyosova, V. (2023). MUROJAAT BIRLIKLARINING IJTIMOIIY-LISONIY TAHLILI. Scientific journal of the Fergana State University, (1), 106-106.
19. Giyosova, V. (2023). GLYUTTONIMLAR BILAN IFODALANGAN BOLALARGA OID MUROJAAT BIRLIKLARI. Scientific journal of the Fergana State University, (6), 163-163.